

**SOCIAL AND ETHNOPSYCHOLOGICAL ADJUSTMENT
FACTORS OF MILITARY SERVANTS AND THEIR FAMILY
MEMBERS**

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Abstract. The article analyzes existing psychological perspectives on the problem of psychological adaptation of military families. The essence of adaptation of women in the family of military personnel is considered in the works of various authors, including the psychological aspects of adaptation of women in the family of military personnel. Objective and subjective criteria of socio-psychological adaptation of military servicemen's family have been determined. The health care of women in the family of military personnel is analyzed, depending on their personal adaptation potential. Ethnopsychological adaptation of military servicewomen is considered. The similarity of the components of flexibility with the structure of communicative competence is noted.

Key words: adjustment, psychological health, personal adjustment potential, educational adjustment, ethnopsychological adjustment, microsocial adjustment.

Introduction: In order to increase the prestige of military service in our country, special attention is paid to the issues of ensuring social protection of military personnel and their family members.

Summarizing the opinions of military psychologists on the studied problem allows to determine the objective and subjective criteria of socio-psychological

adaptation of military personnel. Objective criteria include:

a) adaptation to education - effectiveness and success of educational and professional activities;

b) service-disciplinary adjustment

importance - success in the performance of official tasks, requirements of regulations, orders of commanders and superiors;

v) microsocial adjustment - self-affirmation, a high enough status, a prestigious position in the team as a result of the absence of conflicts with colleagues;

Subjective criteria include:

a) military serviceman's satisfaction with his professional status within the team, maintenance of interest in military profession, military specialty, development of professional interests - motivational flexibility;

b) positive-constructive attitude to team relations, lack of aggressive-conflict or passive-submissive attitude towards others;

c) the presence of adequate, sufficiently high self-esteem with a positive "self-image" ("I-concept"), which implies the absence of internal conflicts, emotional exhaustion, etc. [7].

The generally accepted point of view in military psychology is that adaptive potential determines a person's ability to adapt and is one of the integral indicators of a military person's personality. This statement is based on the recognition that a person has the ability to successfully adapt to a changed environment and the main determinant of the constructive way of development of this process. Its main components are: neuropsychic stability, communication skills, behavior regulation and moral normality.

The identification of communicative abilities as one of the factors of successful adaptation of military servicemen's family confirms the relevance of studying the communicative abilities of women of military servicemen in order to

enrich theoretical data with empirical data, as well as to find new patterns of influence on the studied concepts. In the study conducted by A. G. Maklakov, the dependence of the maintenance of the professional health of military personnel on their personal adaptation potential, as well as the specificity of situations requiring the greatest mobilization (for example, the primary adaptation situation) was analyzed. (to the terms of service). The potential of personal adaptation is considered by the author as a holistic characteristic of a person's mental development, which determines the effectiveness of military-professional adaptation and the possibility of maintaining the professional health of military personnel. A.G. is one of the most important features of personal adaptive potential from the point of view of maintaining mental health. Maklakov refers to the level of neuropsychic stability, self-esteem of the individual, the level of conflict, existing behavioral norms and orientation to the requirements of the community, as well as the presence of communication environment and external social support.

Starting to consider the factors influencing the social adjustment and adjustment of military personnel and their family members, we will cover this issue based on materials taken from the works of various authors. Among the many approaches that reveal the content of social factors, we will focus on the most characteristic ones.

Among the factors of social adjustment O.V. Romashov distinguishes objective and subjective. Objective factors are factors that are less dependent on the adapter. Among them, socio-economic conditions and legal legislation specific to the place of residence of the adapter, potential opportunities for the development of the regional labor market and vocational guidance services, the scope of vocational retraining, the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the workforce, the promotion of existing labor , specialization of industry, etc.

Subjective factors represent a set of certain personal characteristics and

qualities that form a certain behavior: self-confidence, politeness, self-expression, determination, objectivity, etc. includes:

- socio-demographic characteristics of the adapter (gender, age, education, qualification, work experience, social status, etc.);
- socio-psychological (level of aspirations, willingness to work, practicality, speed of orientation to the production situation, self-control and ability to act rationally, communication skills, self-awareness, etc.) the ability to create a sense of responsibility. , etc.);
- sociological (the level of professional interest, the level of material and moral interest in the efficiency and quality of work, the existence of a value orientation to training and education, etc.)¹.

Important subjective factors for the successful adaptation of military personnel and their family members, as well as personality orientation, character, temperament, self-concept, abilities and social motivation.

The materialization of the actions of the adapter in the new social environment includes the influence of the direction of the individual - the set of stable motives that guide his activity and are relatively independent of the existing reality. In general, a direction is a general characteristic of an adapter that describes the target it is aiming for. An adapter can have a social (collective), personal (egoistic) or business orientation. Depending on this, he sets one or another goal. Achieving a set goal indicates a comfortable fit. If insurmountable obstacles appear on the way to the goal, they can lead to maladaptation.

An important place in adaptation is occupied by the self-awareness of the adapter, that is, the level of consciousness that realizes and evaluates its knowledge, abilities, needs, interests and value directions in the future activity in a new social environment. realized. Social adaptation is influenced by personality traits, which reflect a set of stable and important forms of individual characteristics. all the diversity of his attitude to himself, to the people around

him, to his activities. They are indispensable and leave a serious mark on the result of adaptation and can reduce or increase its effectiveness. The presence of a person's abilities (natural talent) allows us to assess how effectively he can act in a civilian environment.

Military sociologists present the correct understanding, selection and active implementation of the directions of spiritual-ethical and socio-economic values as crucial conditions for improving the life efficiency of military personnel and their family members. In this regard, the important tasks of increasing the efficiency of the daily activities of this contingent are as follows: 1) determining (taking into account) its value directions; 2) development (planning) and implementation of proactive management decisions (measures) for timely correction in a favorable direction, and thus to prevent the occurrence of crisis events and their possible negative socio-economic consequences it is desirable to analyze and forecast its changes.

In conclusion, it should be noted that an important place in adaptation is occupied by the adapter's self-awareness, that is, the level of consciousness that realizes and evaluates his knowledge, abilities, needs, interests and values in his future activities in a new social environment. . Social adaptation is influenced by personality traits, which reflect a set of stable and important forms of individual characteristics. All the diversity of his attitude to himself, to the people around him, to his work, they are inseparable and can leave a serious mark on the result of adaptation and reduce or increase its effectiveness. The presence of a person's abilities (natural talent) allows us to assess how effectively he can act in a civilian environment.

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